
WPs-2250-2251 CCN10: “DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site”

[D-2A]

**San Pietro Capofiume HCHO tropospheric profiles and
VCDs dataset from SkySpec-2D MAX-DOAS
measurements and comparisons with TROPOMI
Tropospheric VCDs**

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List of Acronyms

AOD	Aerosol Optical Depth
CINDI	Cabauw Intercomparison of Nitrogen Dioxide Measuring Instruments
CCN	Contract Change Notice
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
DEAP	DOAS optimal Estimation Atmospheric Profile retrieval
DOAS	Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy
FM	Forward Model
FRM4DOAS	Fiducial Reference Measurements for DOAS
ISAC	Istituto di Scienze dell'Atmosfera e del Clima
LOS	Line of Sight
MAX-DOAS	Multi AXis – DOAS
NDACC	Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change
OE	Optimal Estimation
PGN	Pandora Global Network
QA	Quality Assurance
QA4EO	Quality Assurance For Earth Observation
RTM	Radiative Transfer Model
S-5P	Sentinel-5 Precursor
SCD	Slant Column Densities
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SPC	San Pietro Capofiume
TROPOMI	TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument
UV	UltraViolet
VIS	Visible
VCD	Vertical Column Density

1. Introduction

This document is the report of the activities performed in the frame of WPs 2250-1.1, 1.2, 1.3 of the IDEAS-QA4EO WPs-2250-2251 “DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site” CCN10. The WP 2250.1 is centered on the processing of MAX-DOAS SkySpec-2D measurements at San Pietro Capofiume (therein SPC, BO) “Giorgio Fea” ISAC-CNR observatory in the Po Valley for the retrieval of HCHO (formaldehyde) tropospheric profiles.

In this report, we briefly describe the SkySpec-2D system and the HCHO retrieval set-up. We also discuss the results of the SPC HCHO profiles retrievals over one year of data (October 2021-

September 2022) and the comparison of corresponding Tropospheric VCDs with the ones from Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI co-located measurements.

2. HCHO monitoring and MAX-DOAS measurements

Formaldehyde (HCHO) is the most abundant carbonyl compound and a product of oxidization of all primary volatile organic compounds (VOCs). It is emitted from both natural and anthropogenic sources like biomass burning, industrial processes, fossil fuel combustion ([R1], [R2], [R3]), and vegetation [R4]. It has a lifetime of a few hours, its sinks being photolysis at wavelengths shorter than 400 nm, oxidation by OH, and wet deposition. Different studies demonstrated the capability of MAX-DOAS measurements of retrieving aerosol and trace gas concentrations and profiles, including NO₂ and HCHO ([R5], [R6], [R7]). The MAX-DOAS technique exploits the radiation measured at different elevation angles using narrowband absorption features to provide information about tropospheric aerosol and gaseous profiles.

3. The SkySpec-2D system at SPC

The SkySpec-2D-210 (then named as SkySpec-2D) system is developed by Airyx GmbH (https://airyx.de/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/SkySpec-all_2021-03-09.pdf). The SkySpec-2D instrument series allow to perform low- effort, efficient and reliable atmospheric observations with the Passive DOAS method (according to VDI standard 4212). The measurements provide information on the tropospheric and stratospheric concentration and distribution of various trace gases, e.g. NO₂, SO₂, formaldehyde, and aerosol optical depth in UV and VIS (from 300 nm to 550 nm approximately). The SkySpec-2D system, similarly to the TROPOGAS system, is composed of a measurement PC, a case containing the spectrometers, and a telescope. This kind of Airyx instrument represents a state-of-the-art system, and it took part in several FRM4DOAS inter-comparison campaigns, such as the CINDI ones.

The MAX-DOAS acquisition strategy used at SPC is the following: the atmospheric spectra start to be acquired every morning when the SZA becomes lower than 94° (the sun is 4° below the horizon). In the beginning, the SkySpec-2D starts to acquire only zenith-sky spectra. When the SZA becomes lower than 85°, SkySpec-2D starts to perform MAX-DOAS measurements. During MAX-DOAS acquisitions, SkySpec-2D measures in three different azimuth directions: 120°, 225° and 300° from the 1st of October 2021 to the 23rd of March 2022, and 135°, 250° and 315° afterwards (Fig. 1). For each azimuth direction, spectra are acquired at the following elevation angles with respect to the horizon: 1°, 2°, 3°, 5°, 10°, 30° and 90°.

SkySpec-2D has been continuously acquiring MAX-DOAS measurements at the “Giorgio Fea” observatory in SPC since the 1st of October 2021. During all these months, the measurement strategy has remained unchanged except for the azimuth directions selected. Indeed, we decided

to modify them because the telescope, on the 23rd March 2022, was moved and installed in its permanent position (a few meters away from the previous one) and the previous chosen viewing directions were not free from obstacles anymore. The SkySpec-2D was permanently installed on the roof of the shelter containing the PC and spectrometers (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: SkySpec-2D in “Giorgio Fea” observatory at SPC.

4. HCHO MAX-DOAS profiles retrievals from SkySpec-2D measurements

The starting point for HCHO profiles retrieval is the calculation of the HCHO Slant Column Densities (SCDs). As for NO₂ SCDs, HCHO SCDs are calculated by the software QDOAS [R4]. It analyzes all the input spectra contained in the NetCDF files with respect to a reference spectrum, exploiting the DOAS technique. As reference spectrum for the analysis of each MAX-DOAS scan, we chose to use the zenith spectrum of the considered MAX-DOAS scan. The QDOAS settings used for the analysis are reported in Table 1 and an example of retrieved O₄ and HCHO SCDs during 23rd July 2022 is given in Fig. 2. O₄ and HCHO SCDs are retrieved from the UV spectra. The choice of the spectral interval used in the SCDs fit, is the consequence of a deep investigation, necessary due to the high sensitivity of the HCHO SCDs to the fitting interval. Such sensitivity is not present, for example, in the case of NO₂, due to its intense absorption features compared HCHO.

First of all, we fixed the low limit of the spectral interval at 337 nm due to the low spectral counts detected at lower wavelengths. This was necessary even though important HCHO absorption features are also present at lower wavelengths.

No important absorption features are present at wavelengths higher than 360 nm. However, at the beginning, we tested a wider spectral interval, until 390 nm. This choice improved the retrieval of O₄ SCDs but introduced some systematic patterns in the fit residuals, responsible of important systematic errors in the HCHO SCDs.

In conclusion, we decided to reduce the fitting interval to 337-360 nm. Although the noise of the O₄ and HCHO SCDs increases, this choice is more similar to the one adopted by the FRM4DOAS central processing and leads to less systematic effects on the HCHO SCDs.

	HCHO UV	Ref. Cross section
Calibration spectral range	337-365 nm	
Retrieval spectral range	337-360 nm	
Considered XS	NO ₂ 298K	from Van Daele [R8]
	NO ₂ 220K (orto. To NO ₂ 298K)	From Van Daele [R8]
	O ₃ 223K	From Bogumil [R9]
	O ₃ 293K (orto. To O ₃ 223K)	From Bogumil [R9]
	O ₄	From Hermans [R10]
	Ring	Computed according to [R11]
	HCHO	Chance and Orphal[R12]
	BrO	Wilmouth_et_al [R19]
Other fits	Polynomial deg. 5	
	Linear offset order 1	

Table 1: QDOAS settings for the retrieval of the HCHO SCDs.

O₄ SCDs are retrieved as well from SkySpec-2D UV spectra. The O₄ and HCHO SCDs are then processed with the DEAP code used in CCN7 for NO₂ profiles retrievals.

The DEAP algorithm was developed at CNR-ISAC for the retrieval of profiles from MAX-DOAS measurements. The DEAP code is an OE algorithm that exploits the SCIATRAN code as FM and a two steps approach. First, the aerosol extinction profile is retrieved from O₄ SCDs with an iterative procedure. Then, the retrieved profile is used to calculate the NO₂ or HCHO BOX-AMFs, that are used for the retrieval of the gas. The DEAP code uses O₄ and NO₂ (or HCHO) SCDs only, no spectral intensity is used as input. A full algorithm description can be found in [R13].

The retrieval of the aerosol extinction profiles is an iterative process composed of a maximum number of 20 iterations. However, the process can stop previously if the convergence is reached. This happens when the absolute value of the difference between the measured and simulated O₄ SCDs, for each elevation angle, is less than 3 times the O₄ SCD error estimated by the QDOAS fit. At the first iteration, the a-priori extinction profile decreases exponentially with the altitude with a scale height of 1 km⁻¹ and with an AOD of 0.1. At the second iteration the a-priori profile is updated. In particular, it is scaled with the AOD value retrieved during the first iteration. The a-priori errors are 100% of the a-priori profile, with a correlation length of 0.4 km.

The retrieval of the gas profiles is composed of only two iterations. At the first iteration, the a-priori profile decreases exponentially with the altitude with a scale height of 1 km⁻¹ and with a tropospheric VCD equal to the gas SCD measured at the elevation angle of 30°. Sometimes it happens that the SCDs at 30° can be negative, due to the noise. In those cases, the a-priori tropospheric VCD is set to 8x10¹⁵ molec/cm². At the second iteration, the a-priori profile is scaled with the tropospheric VCD retrieved during the first iteration. The a-priori errors are 100% of the a-priori profile, with a correlation length of 0.4 km. The retrieval grid is composed by the following altitudes: 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8, 2.0, 2.2, 2.4, 2.6, 2.8, 3.0 km. The wavelength used for the calculation of the BOX-AMF is 350 nm. The retrieved aerosol extinction and HCHO vertical profiles affected by clouds are filtered out according to the color index of the spectra, as explained in [R14].

Figure 2: Example of O₄ (left) and HCHO (right) SCDs measured at the azimuth direction of 315° on 23rd July 2022 in SPC.

An example of HCHO profiles retrieved from one day of data and corresponding VCDs are reported in Figure 3. As can be noticed from the plot on the left, HCHO exhibits a maximum at about 1.-1.5km, especially in the afternoon, and at ground. This has been noticed also in other

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works [R15]. On a rural site as SPC, with almost no local anthropogenic sources, higher values of HCHO at these levels can be related to long range transport events.

Figure 3: Example of HCHO profiles as a function of altitude and time (left) and VCDs (right) on 23 July 2022 at SPC at the azimuth direction of 315°. The grey profiles and dots refer to the filtered data due to cloud screening.

5. HCHO Tropospheric VCDs dataset at SPC

The results of the HCHO VCDs retrieved from one year of processing at SPC are summarized in Figure 4. The figure shows the HCHO VCDs as a function of the months and of the hours of the day. As can be noticed, HCHO increase in spring and summer and is lower in autumn and winter, as shown in previous works e.g. [R20]. Regarding the diurnal variation, HCHO VCDs reach the maximum in the afternoon in summer and around the middle of the day in winter. The standard deviation is higher in spring and summer at the beginning and end of the day. The number of measurements is almost the same during the year with slightly less measurements in May and August due to instrument failure.

Figure 4: HCHO tropospheric VCDs as a function of month and hour of the day at SPC (left) and corresponding standard deviation (center) and number of measurements (right).

6. Comparison with TROPOMI Satellite HCHO tropospheric VCDs products

TROPOMI is a passive-sensing hyperspectral nadir-viewing imager aboard the S-5P satellite. It was launched in October 2017. S-5P is a near-polar Sun-synchronous orbit satellite flying at an altitude of 817 km, with an overpass local time at ascending node of 13:30 and a repeat cycle of 17 days. TROPOMI has a swath width of approx. 2600 km, and a spatial resolution of 3.5 x 7 (5.5) km at the beginning of the mission (since 6 August 2019). TROPOMI has four separate spectrometers that measure from UV to SWIR, in order to retrieve the concentrations of several atmospheric constituents including O₃, NO₂, SO₂, CO, CH₄, CH₂O and aerosol properties, as well as surface UV radiation. The instrument and the data product have been described in detail by [R16], [R17], and [R18].

For S-5P TROPOMI, we used the OFFL L2 HCHO products. We used only products with a combined quality assurance value (qa_value) higher than 0.75 and of 0.5 as in [R21]. The satellite products were averaged over a circle centered on the SPC observatory.

The results of the comparison between HCHO VCDs from SkySpec and TROPOMI over SPC are reported in Figure 5 and 6. For this exercise, we used a radius of 5 km and 20 km and a temporal mismatch of +/- 15 minutes from TROPOMI overpass (qa_value > 0.75, very similar results using 0.5 as threshold). Varying the time mismatch of the overpass up to +/- 1 hour with a fixed radius, did not make any relevant difference. On the other hand, the variation of the radiuses used for the coincidence up to 20 km around the station affects the results. The 20km radius is also used in works such as [R21] and [R22], while the time intervals used for the comparison may vary. The

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major effects of using the 20 km radius instead of 5 km are that 1) the statistic increased and we had a reduction in the spread of satellite data with STD that goes from 7.6×10^{15} (more than 100%) to 4.4×10^{15} molec/cm² (73%) 2) the average TROPOMI HCHO columns decrease more than the MAX-DOAS one. As can be noticed, TROPOMI HCHO data have a large spread with also negative values and are generally lower than the MAX-DOAS ones especially in Summer. Over one year of data, we get an average HCHO Tropospheric VCD of 7.29×10^{15} molec/cm² from SkySpec-2D and of 6.76×10^{15} molec/cm² from TROPOMI with a bias of about -0.5×10^{15} molec/cm² (-7,5%) for 5km radius and an average HCHO Tropospheric VCD of 7.15×10^{15} molec/cm² from SkySpec-2D and of 6.16×10^{15} molec/cm² from TROPOMI with a bias of about -1.0×10^{16} molec/cm² (-14,8%). The decrease of TROPOMI HCHO VCDs with the radius has already been documented in [R23]. In our case the decrease is of the order of 9% at 20km with respect to 5 km.

Figure 5: Comparison between Tropospheric HCHO VCDs from TROPOMI and SkySpec-2D at “Giorgio Fea” observatory at SPC, in the bottom plots are reported the biases. The radius is 5km around the SPC observatory.

A general underestimation of TROPOMI HCHO Tropospheric column is expected from TROPOMI official validation.

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Figure 6: Same as Figure 5 but with a radius of 20 km.

7. Conclusions

In this report, we described the processing of one year of MAX-DOAS measurements at SPC for the retrievals of HCHO tropospheric profiles, and consequently VCDs. HCHO profiles retrieved at SPC show a peak at about 1-2km altitude. The HCHO VCDs are higher in spring and summer and lower in autumn and winter. HCHO show also a diurnal behaviour with higher values in the central part of the day. When comparing MAX-DOAS HCHO VCDs against TROPOMI satellite measurements, we found that satellite products are on average lower than SkySpec-2D of about $0.5e+15$ molec/cm² (7.5%) using a 5km radius and of $-1.0e+16$ molec/cm² (-14,8%) using 20 km. Both these biases are within the TROPOMI mission requirements (80%) as in [R24].

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